

Full Research Paper

Participation that matters: Expert insights on designing inclusive Living Labs

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Abstract

Living Labs (LLs) are increasingly used as participatory infrastructures, aiming to democratize innovation by involving citizens in co-creation processes. However, despite their inclusive philosophy, many LLs struggle to engage vulnerable communities in meaningful ways. This paper explores strategies to support inclusive citizen engagement in LLs, based on 12 interviews with experts in participatory research and inclusion. Results were structured across barrier type (structural, institutional, and cultural barriers) and the three-layered LL-model (macro, meso, and micro levels). Findings show that inclusion is not a one-time design decision but an ongoing, relational practice requiring flexibility, transparency, and collaboration across researchers, intermediaries, and communities. We argue that to fully realize their potential, LLs must move beyond procedural inclusion toward meaningful participation that amplifies underrepresented voices and addresses power imbalances. The paper concludes with practical recommendations for LL practitioners and policymakers, urging future research that centers citizens' lived experiences to advance inclusive innovation and foster LLs that genuinely address diverse societal needs.

Key words

Inclusivity, Diversity, Vulnerable Citizens, Citizen Engagement, Living Labs

Introduction

Living Labs (LLs) are considered prominent infrastructures for participatory research and innovation. Rooted in real-life contexts, LLs engage diverse stakeholders such as governments, academia, industry, and civil society in co-creating, testing, and evaluating innovations (Ballon et al., 2018). LLs are dynamic, user-centered open innovation ecosystems that integrate research and innovation into everyday settings by bringing together a diverse set of actors (i.e., public institutions, academia, industry, and citizens) within the Quadruple Helix (Schuurman, 2015). By involving users early and continuously throughout innovation processes, LLs aim to develop more socially robust and user-centered technologies (Westerlund et al., 2018). However, the promise of LLs as inclusive spaces for democratic innovation is not always fully realized. Despite their participatory approach, many LLs struggle to meaningfully involve citizens who are often underrepresented in traditional innovation systems, such as people with low digital literacy, migrants, older adults, people with disabilities, or those from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds (Varga et al., 2023).

Inclusion in LLs is not merely an ethical imperative; it is essential to ensure that outcomes reflect the full diversity of society and respond to a wide spectrum of needs. Amplifying vulnerable voices helps to prevent the reproduction of inequalities and contributes to more equitable innovation practices (Veeckman et al., 2023). Yet, in practice, engaging vulnerable citizens in participatory research remains challenging. Existing LLs often lack clear strategies for inclusive engagement or rely on ad hoc approaches that do not adequately address structural barriers (Schroeder et al., 2024). This raises a critical question: how can LLs move beyond tokenistic inclusion to foster participation that genuinely matters? This paper addresses this gap by exploring how LL practitioners navigate the challenges of citizen engagement, particularly in relation to vulnerable groups.

The research builds on the following questions: (1) What strategies do LL practitioners use to overcome barriers to the engagement of vulnerable citizens? (2) How can the design and governance of LLs be improved to support more inclusive engagement of vulnerable communities? Drawing on insights from 12 in-depth interviews with experienced participatory researchers, the paper aims to identify actionable strategies for more inclusive engagement practices. First, we present literature on inclusive participation and LL methodologies. Next, we outline our qualitative research design. We then present key findings from the expert interviews, organized by barrier type and LL governance level. Finally, we discuss implications for the future design and governance of inclusive LLs.

Theoretical Framework

Challenges in Inclusive Citizen Engagement

While LLs are often presented as inherently inclusive, literature highlights considerable challenges in engaging vulnerable citizens. These include risks of tokenism (i.e. the symbolic gesture of minority inclusion aimed at projecting an image of inclusivity), accessibility limitations, and persistent power imbalances between professional actors and participants (Varga et al., 2023). Vulnerable groups, such as people with low digital literacy, migrants, older adults, people with disabilities, or those from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds, often face barriers that hinder participation (Veeckman et al., 2023). Ethical concerns also arise in relation to informed consent, especially when engaging individuals with limited decision-making capacity (Schroeder et al., 2024).

To overcome these barriers, scholars advocate for adaptive and reflexive strategies tailored to the needs of specific groups. These include providing multiple formats for participation, ensuring linguistic and cultural accessibility, working with trusted community gatekeepers, and building long-term relationships rather than relying on short-term engagements (Hodson et al., 2023). Understanding the motivational differences between groups, such as students, retirees, or working adults, also helps in designing more responsive engagement strategies (Asmar et al., 2022; Hodson et al., 2023). The broader literature on Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) within LLs and participatory research provides important insights but also reveals notable gaps (Shamy et al., 2025; Hossain et al., 2019; Varga et al., 2023). There is considerable variation in how EDI is defined and practiced across LLs, often shaped by local contexts, institutional goals, and methodological traditions (Berberi et al., 2023). While many initiatives claim to support diverse participation, few provide systematic evaluation of EDI outcomes. Empirical evidence demonstrating long-term impacts remains scarce (Amann & Sleight, 2021).

Living Labs as Participatory Infrastructures

Key to the functioning of LLs are several foundational pillars. First, LLs emphasize active user engagement, involving citizens not merely as subjects or testers, but as equal contributors throughout all phases of innovation (i.e., from ideation to prototyping and implementation) (Ballon et al., 2018). Second, LLs utilize multi-method approaches to capture and incorporate diverse forms of knowledge (e.g., ethnographic studies, participatory design, co-creation workshops, and action research) (Hossain et al., 2019; Logghe & Schuurman, 2017). Third, they prioritize real-life contextualization, situating innovation processes within the environments and routines of everyday life, thereby enhancing the validity and applicability of outcomes. Finally, LLs rely on multi-stakeholder

coordination, facilitating collaborative networks to enable participatory approaches and open innovation (Westerlund et al., 2018).

Embedded within LL infrastructures are principles of inclusion, citizen engagement, and co-creation, which are considered necessary for participatory research and innovation. Inclusion refers to deliberate efforts to involve individuals and communities who are often underrepresented or marginalized within traditional research and innovation processes (Amann & Sleight, 2021; Varga et al., 2023). This involves reducing barriers to entry and creating empowering spaces for participation. Citizen engagement goes beyond consultation, it encompasses a spectrum of participation from minimal input to deep collaboration, as conceptualized in Arnstein's (1969) ladder of citizen participation. In LLs, citizen engagement typically brings experiential and context-specific knowledge into the innovation process. Co-creation operationalizes this engagement by structuring participatory activities that facilitate shared value creation among all stakeholders (Schuurman et al., 2016)

The Layers of Living Labs

A useful lens for understanding the complexity of LL-operations is the three-layered model proposed by Schuurman (2015) distinguishing macro, meso, and micro levels. At the macro level, LLs are seen as system-level constellations consisting of institutional partnerships and the alignment of open innovation ecosystems. The meso level concerns concrete innovation projects that are conducted within these constellations, characterized by real-life experimentation, collaboration among multiple actors, and a blending of user innovation with open innovation logics. Finally, the micro level refers to different methodological steps and user involvement. This layered structure allows researchers to identify how inclusion and engagement are conceptualized and operationalized across different levels.

LLs offer a promising framework for participatory and inclusive innovation, particularly when analysed through a multi-level lens that highlights the interplay between structure, method, and context. However, realizing their full potential, particularly in engaging vulnerable groups, requires moving beyond procedural inclusion toward meaningful engagement and continuous reflection.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design, using systematizing (i.e., eliciting reflexive expert knowledge through structured, direct questioning) semi-structured expert interviews to examine barriers and strategies for engaging vulnerable citizens in LLs

(Bogner et al., 2014). The aim was to identify recurring patterns as well as process- and context-specific insights (Van Audenhove & Donders, 2019). These insights were drawn from practitioners and researchers with experience and specialized knowledge in engaging vulnerable citizens across a range of institutional settings and innovation projects.

Data Collection

We conducted 12 semi-structured interviews with experts (i.e., project managers, academic researchers, and accessibility and inclusivity experts) identified through the authors’ professional networks and purposive snowball sampling (Bryman, 2016). Participants were selected to ensure diversity in professional background, institutional affiliation, and area of expertise (see Table 1). All interviewees had direct involvement in citizen-centered research and were familiar with co-creation, participatory design, or LL methodologies. Recruitment continued until theoretical saturation was achieved, indicating that no new themes were emerging from the data (Bryman, 2016).

Table 1. Overview Participating Experts

Name	Institution	Experience	Job Title
Expert 1	Imecc-SMIT, VUB, Belgium	15 years	User Researcher in Media Innovation Projects
Expert 2	UniNettuno University, Italy	20 years	Doctor of Philosophy & Professor in Industrial Design
Expert 3	Imecc-SMIT, VUB, Belgium	14 years	Researcher in Digital Inclusion and Citizen Engagement
Expert 4	Vlaamse Radio en Televisie-omroeporganisatie (VRT), Belgium	10 years	Digital Accessibility Expert
Expert 5	Imecc-SMIT, VUB, Belgium	4 years	Researcher Digital Inclusion and Human Rights
Expert 6	Thomas More, Belgium	40 years	Researcher Inclusive Communication for Social-profit Organizations and Government

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Expert 7	Imec-SMIT, VUB, Belgium	7 years	Doctor in Digital Inclusion and Ageism
Expert 8	DemocracyX, Denmark	7 years	Project Management
Expert 9	Thomas More, Belgium	14 years	Researcher Prevention and Empowerment
Expert 10	Mobilise, VUB, Belgium	4 years	Researcher Urban Mobility and Participatory Planning
Expert 11	Anonymised	15 years	Inclusive Health Communication
Expert 12	Anonymised	10 years	Technology Acceptance

Ethical guidelines for qualitative research were strictly followed. All participants received and signed an informed consent form, explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw at any time, and how their data would be handled and stored securely. Given the professional nature of the interviews, ten participants agreed to include their real name, institution, and job title. Two participants opted for anonymisation and only agreed to the sharing of their job title. For these participants, pseudonyms were used, and the institution was left out in internal documentation to maintain confidentiality.

A semi-structured interview guide was developed to ensure thematic consistency across interviews while allowing flexibility. We focused on 1) experts' general experiences with participatory research, 2) challenges of engaging vulnerable citizens, and 3) effective strategies for inclusive participation. Each interview lasted between 55 and 85 minutes and was conducted either in person or online via Microsoft Teams. Four interviews were conducted in English, while the remaining eight were carried out in Dutch. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis. Citations originally in Dutch have been translated to English.

Data Analysis

The interview data were analysed using a Grounded Theory approach (Strauss & Corbin, 1998), allowing concepts and themes to emerge inductively while maintaining a systematic coding structure. The analysis followed three phases. First, open coding was conducted to identify key concepts and recurring challenges related to participation, inclusion, and innovation. Second, axial coding was used to organize relationships between codes around central categories such as barriers, strategies, recommendations,

and contextual conditions, linking strategies to specific challenges. Third, selective coding integrated these categories into a coherent narrative on inclusive participation in LLs. Themes were structured across barrier type (structural, institutional, and cultural) and macro, meso, and micro levels, in alignment with Schuurman’s (2015) three-layered LL model. This structure enabled a systematic mapping of themes, offered a more nuanced understanding of the drivers of citizen exclusion, and facilitated alignment with targeted strategies to enhance inclusivity in LL-research. Throughout the analysis, we engaged in constant comparison, iteratively moving between data and emerging codes to refine categories and prevent premature closure of interpretation (Bryman, 2016).

To ensure trustworthiness, strategies aligned with Lincoln and Guba’s (1985) criteria of transferability, dependability, and confirmability were employed. Transferability was supported through thick descriptions (Geertz, 1973) of findings, participant selection, and data collection. Dependability was strengthened via an audit trail documenting all analytical steps to enhance transparency and reproducibility. Confirmability was addressed through reflexivity and careful tracking of analytical decisions, ensuring findings remained grounded in participants’ perspectives rather than shaped by researcher assumptions.

Results – Challenges and Strategies for Inclusive Engagement

Challenges to Inclusive Citizen Engagement

This study identified eight recurring challenges related to engaging vulnerable citizens in participatory LLs. Table 2 presents an overview of the challenges and their underlying causes, mapping them on barrier type and LL governance model.

Table 2. Mapping of the Challenges on Barrier Type and LL Governance Level

Barrier Type	Level	Rooted in...	LL Challenges
Structural	Macro	Societal systems and inequalities	Recruitment
		LL innovation ecosystem	Time intensity Long-term engagement
Institutional	Meso	Organizational practices	Ethical challenges
		LL organizational set-up	Funding structures Limited agency

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Cultural	Micro	Beliefs, norms, communication styles	Linguistic diversity
		LL user interactions	Power imbalances

Structural barriers refer to deep-rooted societal inequalities which restrict the capacity of vulnerable citizens to engage in research processes (Schroeder et al., 2024). We identified three main challenges that are linked to this societal and systemic context and operate on a macro level. Experts consistently highlighted the difficulty of (1) recruiting vulnerable groups. This challenge is amplified by language barriers, limited social networks, limited accessibility due to low digital presence, and a pervasive mistrust of governments, researchers, or institutions. These are all symptoms of broader systemic exclusion (Asmar et al., 2022). The time-consuming nature of participatory LL research (2) was identified as a major barrier.

“It takes a lot of time, especially those initial phases. That takes a while, right, to really question people. It's not that you have a conversation of a quarter of an hour. You need time to figure out how people want to see certain things, what needs that they have.”
(Expert 1, User Research and Media Innovations Expert)

Iterative and inclusive methods inherently require sustained engagement throughout multiple stages of the research, which can be difficult to balance with the time constraints of both researchers and participants. For vulnerable citizens, limited time and energy due to financial insecurity or care responsibilities (Varga et al., 2023) often make reiterating participation unsustainable and -manageable. Further, maintaining long-term engagement of participants (3) proved challenging and emerged as a complicating barrier to citizen engagement. Experts noted high dropout rates and limited continuity, particularly when participants did not perceive immediate or tangible personal benefits. While incentives (e.g., compensation, gift cards) are helpful, they often fall short in ensuring sustained involvement, especially when structural living conditions are unstable.

Institutional barriers are linked to the rules, practices, and funding mechanisms of organizations that unintentionally exclude citizens from meaningful participation (Amann & Sleigh, 2021) Three challenges fall into this category and operate on a meso level, embedded in organizational structures, institutional practices, and the design of the LL itself (Schuurman, 2015). Ethical challenges (4) emerged as a recurring concern when engaging vulnerable groups. Participants with limited literacy or cognitive challenges often face difficulties understanding informed consent procedures, while researchers

struggle to adapt ethical protocols to their needs. Institutional ethics requirements, often lack flexibility for inclusive participatory research.

Funding structures (5) were also cited as a key limitation. Experts emphasized that project resources are frequently allocated to technological development, while insufficient funding is reserved for citizen engagement. This imbalance constrains participatory activities and limits their quality and reach. Budgetary inflexibility subsequently affects the ability to compensate participants or conduct extensive outreach. Finally, many experts described how citizens have limited influence on end-products (6). While participation is often emphasized in early stages, final decisions remain in the hands of institutional actors, such as technical partners or policymakers.

“We have partners working on engagement or social science partners understanding what this is all about. Actually, making sure the results are used by the technical partners is a challenge (...) If that doesn't work out, then it doesn't really matter that we did great participatory work.” (Expert 8, Expert Project Management)

This reinforces top-down processes and risks “participation washing”, a symbolic rather than substantive involvement of vulnerable citizens.

Cultural barriers arise from misalignments in communication styles, values, norms, and expectations between researchers and participants, particularly across social or cultural divides (Sands et al., 2007). Two challenges within this category are primarily situated at the micro level, manifesting in interactions with users throughout the LL process (Schuurman, 2015). Linguistic diversity and communication complexity (7) were frequently mentioned as barriers to inclusive participation.

“I think the issue of language is often underestimated. Because not everyone speaks Dutch equally well. How do you deal with that? Not everyone can read. How do you deal with that?” (Expert 7, Digital Inclusion and Ageism Expert)

Engaging non-native speakers or participants with hearing, visual, or literacy difficulties often requires interpreters or translated materials. However, experts pointed out that such translations frequently result in a loss of nuance, which undermines the depth and accuracy of participant input. Power imbalances in mixed-group settings (8) were also cited as significant. In discussions involving both vulnerable citizens and highly educated or technically skilled participants (i.e., an audience reflecting societal diversity), the latter group often dominates the conversation. As a result, the voices of more vulnerable participants may be silenced or self-censored, leading to skewed and non-diverse

outcomes. Facilitators are required to be especially sensitive to these dynamics and actively manage group interactions.

Effective Strategies for Inclusive Citizen Engagement

Inclusive LLs require addressing the multifaceted barriers that often prevent vulnerable groups from meaningful engagement. Drawing on expert insights, this section outlines 14 strategies that have proven effective in mitigating the challenges presented above. They will be systematically categorized and mapped, following the same approach applied to the outlined challenges (see Table 3).

Table 3. Mapping of the Strategies on Barrier Type and LL Governance Level

Barrier Type	Level	Rooted in...	LL Challenges	Engagement Strategies
Structural	Macro	Societal systems and inequalities	Recruitment	Incentives, compensation
		LL innovation ecosystem	Time intensity	Flexibility
Institutional	Meso	Organizational rules and practices	Ethical challenges	Practical support
		LL organizational set-up	Funding structures	Format accessibility
			Limited agency	Intermediaries
Cultural	Micro	Beliefs, norms, communication styles	Linguistic diversity	Training
			Power imbalances	Safe environments
		LL user interactions		Transparency, clarity

Engagement Strategies for Structural Barriers – Macro

To address the highlighted structural barriers and challenges, rooted in broader structural inequalities and manifested at a macro level (i.e., difficulties in recruitment, the time-consuming nature of LLs, and long-term participation), experts shared a range of practical strategies aimed at mitigating these barriers and fostering more inclusive citizen involvement in participatory LLs. Offering incentives and compensation (1), such as food, vouchers, or financial payments, is commonly used to both acknowledge participants' time and effort and reimburse potential costs. While not a universal solution, such gestures can signal respect and lower the participation threshold:

“In a way, also compensating. I think, uh, when people put some time in it, it's fair that they get paid. Um, but if for ethical reasons or project policy (...) it is not possible that there's maybe some form of snacks, food, drinks, uh, or a ticket to (...) go for a lunch or something” (Expert 10, Mobility and Participation Expert).

Ensuring flexibility in time and location (2) emerged as essential. This includes organizing sessions at times that suit participants' routines (e.g., evenings or weekends) and in locations that are easily accessible or already familiar to the community. In some cases, researchers travel to participants' homes or local centers, thereby minimizing the burden on individuals.

Providing practical support (3), such as childcare during sessions, assistance with transportation, or guidance throughout the process, was also highlighted as a key enabler of inclusion. Several experts mentioned the importance of blended approaches, combining online and offline methods to accommodate different preferences and capacities, especially important for people with limited mobility or digital access.

“So, you kind of have to accommodate them in a very different way. (...) you need to make sure that you can take care of their kids in the same time (...) but I also think that it's sometimes just about (...) timing, knowing when, trying to be curious about what's the place to meet them (...) is that the kind of workplace where you can spend your work hours on a workshop, or is it one where you have to do it after work? Like, these kind of considerations.” (Expert 8, Expert Project Management)

Moreover, adapting formats to ensure physical and cognitive accessibility (4) was identified as critical. This includes simplifying materials, using visuals or alternative communication formats, and ensuring that digital tools are easy to navigate. Selecting appropriate formats requires critical reflection on the specific characteristics and needs of the target group, as well as collaboration with intermediary organizations.

Experts frequently turn to intermediaries (5), including NGOs, community leaders, or trusted organizations, who act as gatekeepers and can help bridge the gap between research teams and participants. These actors often have established relationships and contextual knowledge that enable more effective and sensitive recruitment. Three-step recruitment processes involving initial contact, follow-up, and personal engagement, were recommended to build trust and allow potential participants time to consider their involvement. Experts stressed the importance of investing significant time and resources in recruitment, particularly when working with hard-to-reach groups.

Providing training or hands-on support (6) to facilitate the use of unfamiliar technologies can further promote inclusion, particularly in digital or hybrid settings, and foster sustained engagement by reinforcing a sense of learning and personal development.

“Also doing short trainings before starting the co-design workshops for instance, because we know that not all participants have the same knowledge about the topics, and it also touches a lot upon the confidence that they have to contribute.” (Expert 10, Mobility and Participation Expert)

Finally, the importance of creating comfortable, welcoming environments was emphasised (7). This involves hosting sessions in familiar community spaces, offering refreshments, and designing interactions to reduce stress or intimidation. These seemingly minor details can have a substantial impact on whether individuals feel safe and respected enough to participate.

Engagement Strategies for Institutional Barriers – Meso

To overcome institutional barriers (i.e., ethical challenges, funding structures, and limited participant agency) to inclusive citizen engagement, ensuring transparency and clarity of expectations (8) is essential. From the early stages, participants should be clearly informed about the project’s objectives, their expected roles, and the anticipated outcomes. Emphasizing a genuine interest in their perspectives, without framing responses as right or wrong, fosters transparency, helps to reduce power imbalances, and supports the development of mutual trust.

“Really giving them the feeling of you can't make mistakes here. We are looking for your experience, so there are no wrong answers. I think it's a barrier to participate in something you don't know.” (Expert 1, User Research and Media Innovations Expert)

Feedback loops (9) were considered necessary to demonstrate impact and ensure accountability. Informing participants how their input was used, or sharing outcomes of the research, can validate their contributions and foster longer-term engagement. Some

experts involved citizens in dissemination activities, such as co-presenting results or co-creating outputs, which enhances their sense of ownership and influence.

“The big moment of feedback then logically always comes at the end of the project. We do that in different ways. It can just be by sharing a report, (...) more accessible science communication through a blog or a video. Sometimes there is also a kind of gathering where someone explains the results.” (Expert 3, Citizen Engagement Expert)

On the other hand, this approach also fosters a sense of participant engagement and underscores the value and importance of citizen input for external institutions or project partners. This can, in turn, enhance the impact of citizen feedback on the final outcomes. Subsequently, a broader shift in mindset was also emphasized: viewing participants as co-creators rather than research subjects (10). This involves avoiding forms of engagement that treat participants only as sources of information or short-term contributors. Instead, it emphasizes building relationships based on mutual respect, two-way exchange, and shared learning.

Finally, experts underscored the importance of acknowledging the researcher’s own accountability throughout the LL research process (11). In participatory research involving vulnerable citizens, it is the responsibility of the researcher to ensure that ethical guidelines are upheld while translating them into accessible and understandable formats for participants. Additionally, researchers bear the responsibility of advocating for participants’ input to be meaningfully considered by institutional actors and reflected in the final outcomes.

“It’s our responsibility. Yes. Or its most of our responsibility. I think it’s important to reach out to the right people. It’s important to disseminate your results, your recommendations, your conclusions.” (Expert 5, Digital Inclusion and Human Rights Expert)

Engagement Strategies for Cultural Barriers – Micro

Cultural barriers (i.e. linguistic diversity and power imbalances), operating at the micro level, can hinder inclusive engagement by limiting the accuracy of participant input and silencing less dominant voices, thus requiring careful facilitation and inclusive communication strategies. To address these, experts consistently highlighted the importance of tailoring language and avoiding academic or institutional jargon (12). Communication should be clear, accessible, and adapted to the specific context and audience. Using a warm, empathetic, and human interaction and moderation style (13) can reduce perceived distance, both between researchers and participants and among participants.

"I always start with a bit of personal stories, looking for common ground. Something that you share with your vulnerable target group. What you show as a person and not so much as a researcher. You must not place yourself above your research participants." (Expert 11, Inclusive Health Communication Expert)

An intersectional lens was deemed necessary to recognize and respect the diverse identities and needs within communities. Cultural relevance and inclusivity in communication styles and formats, such as multilingual materials or using symbols and metaphors meaningful to the community, further facilitate inclusive engagement.

Framing research in ways that are relatable and empowering (e.g., by focusing on participants' strengths and lived experiences rather than deficits) can enhance motivation and self-confidence. Long-term relationship-building (14) and trust were described as crucial, especially for communities that have historically been overlooked or misrepresented in research. Experts emphasized the importance of being present, non-judgmental, and compassionate as a researcher.

"In my own research with older adults on digital inclusion, we didn't approach it from 'Tell us about your poor health, old person'. No, we came from 'What are you good at in digital technology? What do you enjoy about digital technology?'" (Expert 7, Digital Inclusion and Ageism Expert)

Embodying these values not only supports ethical practice but also builds the connection necessary for authentic engagement and enhances participants willingness to raise their voice in diverse groups.

Discussion - Designing Inclusive Living Labs

The findings of this study underline that inclusion in LLs is not a one-time intervention but an ongoing, adaptive practice that requires continuous reflection and responsiveness. Practical design considerations, such as space, time, and facilitation emerged as central to enabling or constraining participation. Structural barriers like time intensity, recruitment, or long-term engagement frequently prevent vulnerable citizens from engaging meaningfully. Institutional barriers like inflexible ethical procedures, limited funding, and top-down decision-making often prevent sustained and empowering citizen involvement. Cultural barriers, including language differences and power imbalances, can create disconnects between researchers and participants. Echoing prior research, strategies such as flexible scheduling and support, accessible formats, clearer communication, feedback loops, empathetic moderation, and trust- and relationship-building proved essential to mitigating these barriers and creating enabling environments

(Amann & Sleight, 2021; Hodson et al., 2023; Varga et al., 2023; Schroeder et al., 2024; Veeckman et al., 2023).

Importantly, inclusion should be embedded across all levels of the LL process, from ideation to evaluation and macro to micro (see Figure 1), and not treated as a box-ticking exercise, aligning with Schuurman's (2015) emphasis on reflexivity and sustained engagement. Building trust takes time and must be accounted for in project timelines and budgets. Experts emphasized that short-term engagements and rigid project cycles undermine the possibility for deeper collaboration, particularly with vulnerable groups.

Figure 1. Designing Inclusive Living Labs

A clear implication is the need to collaborate across stakeholder boundaries (see Figure 1). Inclusion cannot rest solely on the shoulders of researchers. Partnerships with intermediary organizations, such as NGOs or community leaders, are vital for accessing and engaging communities. These actors often have the trust, language, and contextual knowledge that academic institutions lack (Hodson et al., 2023). Additionally, involving participants not only as data providers but as co-creators helps shift power balances and enhance relevance and ownership. This approach resonates with LL Quadruple Helix collaborations (Schuurman, 2015), but it requires conscious effort to overcome institutional hierarchies (Amann & Sleight, 2021).

Compared to existing literature, this study adds specificity by distinguishing between structural, institutional, and cultural barriers, and by mapping targeted strategies for each. While many LLs claim to promote Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI), concrete operationalizations remain vague (Berberi et al., 2023). Our findings provide a more nuanced and practical guide for implementation, such as prioritizing lived experience over formal expertise, using inclusive language, and offering valuable feedback loops. These

strategies are scalable and adaptable and could inform EDI indicators or guidelines at both project and policy levels.

However, tensions between innovation goals and inclusivity goals were evident. Innovation agendas often prioritize speed, novelty, and efficiency, values that conflict with the slow, relational, and care-driven work required for inclusive engagement. These tensions must be acknowledged and managed rather than ignored. Embedding inclusive practices may slow down innovation but enhances its social robustness and legitimacy (Schroeder et al., 2024). Finally, the findings prompt reflection on the role of experts versus community voices. While expert knowledge is indispensable for navigating complex systems and designing facilitation tools, it must not overshadow the experiential knowledge of participants.

Conclusion

This study identified three key categories of barriers - structural, institutional, cultural – and LL governance levels – macro, meso, micro - that hinder the meaningful inclusion of vulnerable citizens in LLs. Challenges and strategies were mapped, highlighting practical and relational approaches to foster inclusive participation. Findings stress that overcoming these barriers requires deliberate, context-sensitive efforts throughout the research process. For LL practitioners and policymakers, we recommend investing in flexible formats, sustained trust-building, inclusive communication, and structural support such as childcare and compensation. Policymakers should also revise funding and ethical frameworks to accommodate the slower, relationship-based nature of inclusive research. This study has its limitations as it does not fully capture the experiences of vulnerable groups. Future research should foreground the perspectives of citizens themselves, particularly those often excluded from participatory processes. Exploring their lived experiences, expectations, and motivations could refine and humanize current engagement strategies. It is also important to recognize that vulnerability is not a uniform category. Future work should distinguish between different types of vulnerability as these may shape participation in different ways. Ultimately, LLs hold potential as drivers of systemic change, but only if they centre equity and inclusion as core values rather than peripheral concerns. By embedding inclusive practices into their DNA, LLs can help reshape innovation processes.

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